

"THE SIGNIFICANCE OF ANTI-THYROPEROXIDASE ANTIBODY TITER IN PREDICTING RECURRENCE IN PATIENTS WITH DIFFUSE TOXIC GOITER

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ABSTRACT

Graves' disease (GD), or diffuse toxic goiter (DTG), is an autoimmune thyroid disorder caused by antibodies stimulating the thyroid-stimulating hormone (TSH) receptor. Measurement of TSH receptor antibodies (TRAb) is useful for predicting recurrence of DTG after antithyroid drug (ATD) therapy. However, the association of other thyroid autoantibodies with DTG recurrence remains unclear.

Graves' disease (GD), or diffuse toxic goiter (DTG), is an autoimmune thyroid disorder caused by antibodies stimulating the thyroid-stimulating hormone (TSH) receptor. Measurement of TSH receptor antibodies (TRAb) is useful for predicting recurrence of DTG after antithyroid drug (ATD) therapy. However, the association of other thyroid autoantibodies with DTG recurrence remains unclear.

Treatment options for hyperthyroidism in Graves' disease include antithyroid drugs, radioactive iodine therapy, or surgery. A recent worldwide survey of 730 physicians showed significant geographic variation in preferred first-line therapy for the initial episode of DTG-related hyperthyroidism. In the United States, radioactive iodine therapy is the first choice in 58.6% of cases, whereas in Europe, antithyroid drugs are preferred (85.7%) over radioactive iodine (13.3%). Treatment choice may shift in the presence of Graves' orbitopathy, large goiter, or pregnancy planning. Therapy should be individualized, considering comorbidities and patient preferences. The probability of remission after a course of antithyroid drugs is an important factor in treatment selection. If remission probability is low, thyroidectomy or radioactive iodine therapy may be preferable. Overall remission rates after antithyroid drug therapy range from 30–50%, with geographic differences in iodine intake explaining part of the variation. Several factors partially predict recurrence risk after ATD therapy, including younger age (<40 years), severe biochemical disease, high thyroid-binding immunoglobulin (TBII) levels, large goiter, and smoking. Most studies, however, assessed prognostic factors at the time of ATD withdrawal rather than at diagnosis. Studies evaluating prognostic parameters prior to treatment have identified large goiter and higher biochemical severity as risk factors, while the contribution of age, sex, smoking, and TRAb levels varies. We aimed to investigate whether known DTG susceptibility genes could help predict recurrence. Limited data exist on genetic influences on recurrence after ATD therapy, and published studies across different ethnic groups show conflicting results.

Objective: To study the role of TRAb antibodies in predicting recurrence in patients with diffuse toxic goiter.

Materials and Methods: Clinical data were collected at City Clinical Hospital No. 1 in Andijan. A total of 62 patients were examined, including 42 women and 20 men, with a mean age of 49.2 ± 1.62 years (women: 47 ± 1.76 years; men: 42 ± 2.6 years). Among the 62 patients receiving conservative treatment for DTG, 47 achieved full remission. Regarding severity of thyrotoxicosis, 19 (30.6%) had mild, 28 (45.2%) moderate, and 15 (24.2%) severe disease. Recurrence occurred in 15 patients (24.2%) two years after conservative treatment, leading to total thyroidectomy. Thus, 47 patients formed the main group (medical therapy), and 15 formed the recurrence group (medical therapy + thyroidectomy). A control group included 20 healthy individuals (10 women, 10 men), whose hormonal results were used for reference.

Inclusion criteria: diffuse toxic goiter, men and women.

Exclusion criteria: disorders of carbohydrate metabolism, ischemic heart disease, congenital heart defects, idiopathic cardiomyopathies, and history of cerebrovascular accidents.

Study methods: clinical assessment, biochemical (bilirubin, direct and indirect, ALT, AST, PTI, coagulation, CRP), hormonal (TSH, free thyroxine, TRAb, prolactin), anthropometric measurements (height, weight, BMI, waist and hip circumference), and instrumental methods (ECG, Echo-CG, thyroid and abdominal ultrasound, chest X-ray). Baseline evaluation included medical history, physical exam (heart rate, blood pressure), laboratory testing of free T3, free T4, TSH, and TRAb antibodies. Hormones were measured using HUMAN reagents (Germany). Data were analyzed using Microsoft Office Excel 2003.

Results: After conventional treatment, remission was achieved in 47 patients (75.4%) in the main group, whereas the combined conservative approach led to remission in only 15 patients (26.2%). The most significant deviations in immune and hormonal parameters were observed in patients with severe thyrotoxicosis, who also experienced recurrence and later underwent surgery. One month after total thyroidectomy, recurrence group patients, as well as those on conservative therapy, demonstrated normalization and postoperative hypothyroidism.

Conclusions: The study revealed a significant difference in treatment effectiveness: conventional therapy led to remission in the majority (75.4%), whereas the complex conservative approach achieved remission in only 26.2%. Monitoring TRAb antibody levels during treatment may help predict recurrence in patients positive for TRAb at diagnosis who are receiving antithyroid drugs

References:

1. Choi YM, Kwak MK, Hong SM, Hong EG. Changes in Thyroid Peroxidase and Thyroglobulin Antibodies Might Be Associated with Graves' Disease Relapse after Antithyroid Drug Therapy. *Endocrinol Metab (Seoul)*. 2019 Sep;34(3):268–274. doi: 10.3803/EnM.2019.34.3.268
2. Allahabadi A, Daykin J, Holder RL, Sheppard MC, Gough SC, Franklyn JA. Age and gender predict the outcome of treatment for Graves' hyperthyroidism. *J Clin Endocrinol Metab*. 2000 Mar;85(3):1038–1042. doi: 10.1210/jcem.85.3.6430
3. Schleusener H, Schwander J, Fischer C, Holle R, Holl G, Badenhop K, Hensen J, Finke R, Bogner U, Mayr WR, et al. Prospective multicentre study on the prediction of relapse after

- antithyroid drug treatment in patients with Graves' disease. *Acta Endocrinol (Copenh)*. 1989 Jun;120(6):689–701. doi: 10.1530/acta.0.1200689
- 4.Vitti P, Rago T, Chiovato L, Pallini S, Santini F, Fiore E, Rocchi R, Martino E, Pinchera A. Clinical features of patients with Graves' disease undergoing remission after antithyroid drug treatment. *Thyroid*. 1997 Jun;7(3):369–375. doi: 10.1089/thy.1997.7.369
- 5.Winsa B, Dahlberg A, Jansson R, Agren H, Karlsson FA. Factors influencing the outcome of thyrostatic drug therapy in Graves' disease. *Acta Endocrinol (Copenh)*. 1990 Jun;122(6):722–728. doi: 10.1530/acta.0.1220722
- 6.Yamada T, Aizawa T, Koizumi Y, Komiya I, Ichikawa K, Hashizume K. Age-related therapeutic response to antithyroid drug in patients with hyperthyroid Graves' disease. *J Am Geriatr Soc*. 1994 May;42(5):513–516. doi: 10.1111/j.1532-5415.1994.tb04973.x
- 7.Kimball LE, Kulinskaya E, Brown B, Johnston C, Farid NR. Does smoking increase relapse rates in Graves' disease? *J Endocrinol Invest*. 2002 Feb;25(2):152–157. doi: 10.1007/BF03343979
- 8.Werner SC, Ingbar SH. Werner & Ingbar's *The Thyroid: A Fundamental and Clinical Text*. Lippincott Williams & Wilkins, 2005. p. 549
- 9.Kimura H, Kato Y, Shimizu S, Takano K, Sato K. Association of polymorphism at position 49 in exon 1 of the cytotoxic T-lymphocyte-associated factor 4 gene with Graves' disease refractory to medical treatment, but not with amiodarone-associated thyroid dysfunction. *Thyroid*. 2009 Sep;19(9):975–981. doi: 10.1089/thy.2009.0066
- 10.Wang PW, Chen IY, Juo SH, Hsi E, Liu RT, Hsieh CJ. Genotype and phenotype predictors of relapse of Graves' disease after antithyroid drug withdrawal. *Eur Thyroid J*. 2013 Jan;1(4):251–258. doi: 10.1159/000342621